

EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

Two systems of extension coverage in southern Sri Lanka

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The Training and Visit (T&V) System for agricultural extension was introduced in Sri Lanka in 1979-80. Village extension workers (VEWs) of the Department of Agriculture had been carrying out village-level agricultural extension programs until 1990 when the VEWs were transferred to decentralized provincial councils. This study compares the extension coverage under the two systems in the southern rice-growing district of Matara.

We collected data for the main cropping seasons of 1986-87 and 1990-91 by interviewing 100 randomly selected rice farmers during each season.

Degree of interaction between VEWs and farmers was classified into no

Farmers (no.)

Extension coverage under different management systems, Matara, Sri Lanka.

interaction, one interaction in 3 mo, one in 2 mo, and one in 1 mo (see figure).

The number of farmers who did not interact with a VEW increased significantly under the new system. Farmers who had one interaction/month declined over the reference period. The χ^2 test

implies that a significant difference at 0.01 level exists between the two extension systems in terms of degree of interaction. The shift from T&V to the provincial council system resulted in declining extension contacts. ■

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Validation of BLASTSIM.2 model in IRRI blast (Bl) nursery and Cavinti, Laguna, Philippines

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We simulated leaf Bl epidemics under tropical conditions using BLASTSIM.2, a computer-based simulation model programed in FORTRAN. The model is potentially useful to understand development of Bl epidemics in different tropical rice management systems.

The model follows the typical leaf Bl monocycle consisting of stages (the state variables in the model) of spore production, spore release, spore deposition, latency, penetration and colonization, lesion production, and lesion development. Several interacting climatic,

Results of regression, correlation, and pooled-variance analyses of observed versus model-predicted lesion number/hill, lesion size/hill, and % disease severity/hill, 1989 WS and 1991 DS.^a

Treatment	State variable	R ²	r	F	Pooled variance
<i>Cavinti, 1989 WS</i>					
Low epidemic	Lesion no.	0.77	0.88**	255.08**	301.15 ns
	Lesion size	0.86	0.92**	460.96**	3.23 ns
	Severity	0.91	0.95**	797.37**	1.17 ns
Medium epidemic	Lesion no.	0.55	0.74**	95.92**	2673.87**
	Lesion size	0.61	0.78**	122.63**	20.44**
	Severity	0.73	0.86**	215.41**	8.91**
High epidemic	Lesion no.	0.76	0.87**	251.80**	2426.10*
	Lesion size	0.95	0.97**	1414.71**	15.21 ns
<i>IRRI, 1991 DS</i>					
10-cm spacing	Lesion no.	0.86	0.93**	516.31**	8669.35 ns
	Lesion size	0.94	0.97**	1409.70**	59.44 ns
	Severity	0.92	0.96**	990.07**	2.69 ns
20-cm spacing	Lesion no.	0.72	0.85**	215.23**	5.82 ns
	Lesion size	0.72	0.85**	217.34**	1254.83*
	Severity	0.77	0.88**	276.32**	0.07 ns

^ans = no significant difference, * = significant difference at 5%, ** = significant difference at 1%.